

Research Article

Communication Issues Faced by Indian Undergraduate Students in Canada

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Introduction

The ability to communicate in a foreign country has been troubling the students for a long time. According to a study done by Gebregergis (2018), one of the major contributing factors to depression among international students was a lack of confidence to communicate in the local language. Additionally, difficulties with English as a language to communicate was a big challenge in adapting to a new academic environment (Kristiana et al., 2022). In India, even though students have a choice to study in colleges with international collaboration, they still aspire to pursue higher education abroad (Gopinath, 2015) due to scholarship, country image, program structure, and social media (Kazako et al., 2017). According to the Indian Ministry of External Affairs, the total number of Indian students enrolled in undergraduate courses across 79 countries during 2022 was 13,24,954 and Canada was second highest with 183,310 students (India, 2023).

This has caused a myriad of problems for international undergraduate students in Canada. To begin with, Parnter (2022) found that 52% of students plagiarised in their academic papers. This was because they had failed to understand the classroom instructions. Secondly, Hashemi (2011) cited in Dewi Zakiya et al. (2022) mentions that students who study at foreign universities frequently claim to feel stressed, nervous, or anxious while learning to speak the language. This is primarily due to the differences in social contexts and cultural environments between learning a first and second foreign language. They also assert that they are mentally resistant to learning English. Thirdly, the mental health of an international student directly correlates with the adjustment problems faced post moving to an English-speaking environment (Can et al., 2021) and, according to this paper, the top area of concern is language issues.

The research topic of Communication issues encountered by Indian undergraduate students at Canadian Colleges and Universities aims to understand students' perspectives and

oppose the belief that the students are responsible for these issues. First, Dewi Zakiya et al. (2022) assert that students' failure to communicate in English was due to their fear of being ridiculed. They contend that students need to be properly directed before moving to an English-speaking country for higher education. In addition, Parnter (2022) concluded that semantics, grammar, and cultural knowledge were all unfamiliar concepts to the pupils from students from Asia who had this issue mostly because they didn't utilize English as their primary language of communication at home. However, Christensen Hughes & Eaton (2022) claim that educational institutions are to blame for such issues since they allow underqualified students to sign up for courses. Their investigation also revealed that over half of the writers of peer-reviewed publications didn't undergo routine plagiarism checks. Moreover, university/college policies and actions should also be held accountable for poor communication rather than only placing the responsibility on students.

This research topic is also important since the dependence on essay writing services and the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is also on the rise in Canada. According to Adlington and Eaton (2021), the contract cheating business is valued globally at approximately USD 15 billion. This is alarming as the rise in such malpractices could be due to the inability of international students to understand classroom instructions. The companies which sell essays in Canada are fully legal (Boisvert, 2019). These companies claim that these essays are written by doctorate-level writers. The use of AI apps such as ChatGPT have gained popularity amongst students in colleges and universities. According to a report by Janzen and Milian (2023), 46% of students in colleges and 68% in universities are familiar with ChatGPT and use it in their routine academic work. Furthermore, Bailey (2020) found out that more than 60% of Canadian students admitted to having cheated on their papers.

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